

AGRICULTURAL MARKETING REFORMS IN INDIA: INTERVENTION OF MODEL APMC ACT-2003

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Abstract

Organized marketing of agricultural commodities is being promoted in the country through a network of regulated markets. Most of the States and Union Territories have enacted legislations (the Agriculture Produce Marketing Committee [APMC] Act) to provide for regulation of agricultural produce markets. Seventeen States/ UTs have amended their APMC Acts and the remaining are in the process of doing so. There are 7157 regulated markets in the country as on 31 March 2010. The country has 21,221 rural periodical markets, about 15 per cent of which function under the ambit of regulation. The advent of regulated markets has helped mitigate the market handicaps of producers/ sellers at wholesale assembling level. Internet connectivity is being provided to important agricultural markets in the country to establish a nationwide information network for speedy collection of prices and market-related information. Presently, wholesale prices of 300 commodities and about 2000 varieties are being reported on the Agricultural Marketing Information Network (AGMARKNET) portal from more than 1900 markets. But rural periodic markets in general and tribal markets in particular have remained outside the ambit of the APMC Act. Other major initiatives include setting up of terminal market complexes (TMC) for fruits, vegetables, and other perishables in important urban centres in those States which provide for market reforms as per the Model Act. These markets will provide state-of-the-art infrastructure facilities for electronic auction, cold chain and logistics, and operate through primary collection centres conveniently located in producing areas to allow easy access to farmers. With this background the present study is aimed to study the APMC model act reforms in various states and also to issues and avenues related to horticulture produce. The study made based on secondary data obtained from many government reports, journals, books and other internet sources. The study result reveals that model legislation provides for the establishment of Private Markets/Yards, Direct Purchase Centres, Consumer and Farmers Markets for direct sale and promotion of Public Private Partnership in the management and development of agricultural markets in the country. The Act also provides for the constitution of State Agricultural Produce Marketing Standards Bureau for promotion of Grading, Standardization and Quality Certification of agricultural produce. The study also highlights that reforming institution improving marketing conditions and encouraging private sector participation, requires reforming the Agricultural Produce Marketing Committee (APMC) Act and abolishing the Essential Commodities Act (ECA). The issues related to horticulture sector, Suggestions have been made that fruits and vegetables should be exempted from Agricultural Produce Marketing committee Act (APMC) regulations and that the grower should be allowed to sell directly to food processors, consolidators or retailers. These steps are particularly relevant for the high value segment that is currently hostage to high post harvest losses and weak farm-to-firm linkages.

Key words: Agricultural Markets, APMC, Grading, Standardisation and Quality Certification.

Introduction

Agricultural Markets in most parts of the Country are established and regulated under the State APMC Acts. The whole geographical area in the State is divided and declared as a market area wherein the markets are managed by the Market Committees constituted by the State Governments. Once a particular area is declared a market area and falls under the jurisdiction of a Market Committee, no person or agency is allowed freely to carry on wholesale marketing activities. The monopoly of Government regulated wholesale markets has prevented development of a competitive marketing system in the country, providing no help to farmers in direct marketing, organizing retailing, a smooth raw material supply to agro-processing industries and adoption of innovative marketing system and technologies (Acharya, S.S., and Agarwal, N.L., 1998).

An efficient agricultural marketing is essential for the development of the agriculture sector as it provides outlets and incentives for increased production, the marketing system contribute greatly to the commercialization of subsistence farmers. Worldwide Governments have recognized the importance of liberalized agriculture markets (Sivanappan, 2000, Ramkishaen, 2004 and Pathak, 2009). Task Force on Agricultural Marketing Reforms set up by the Ministry has suggested promotion of new and competitive Agricultural Market in private and cooperative sectors to encourage direct marketing and contract farming programmes, facilitate industries and large trading companies to undertake procurement of agricultural commodities directly from the farmer's fields and to establish effective linkages between the farm production and retail chains (Patnaik, 2011). There is a necessity to integrate farm production with national and international markets to enable farmers to undertake market driven production plan and adoption of modern marketing practices.

Inter-ministerial group (IMG) on inflation has made a formal pitch to the government for permitting FDI in multi-brand retail in a bid to tackle inflation. The first position paper prepared under the leadership of the chief economic advisor, Kaushik Basu embarks on an entry to

multi-brand retail and reforms in the Agriculture Produce Marketing (APMC) model Act. Even Finance minister in his speech of the annual budget 2011-12, said that In view of the recent episode of inflation, there was a need for the state government to review and enforce a reformed agriculture produce marketing act (Sharma, 2017, Rajagopal, 1993 and Lele, 1971). It was a clear indication to the states to amend their APMC act as per the Model APMC Act 2003. Agriculture marketing is following a protectionism policy. The introduction of the Model APMC Act in 2003 was directed towards allowing private market yards, direct buying and selling and also to promote and regulate contract farming in high value agriculture.

General Features Of Agricultural Marketing

Agricultural marketing system can be analyzed by looking at the farmers' marketing practices, marketing channels and the structure of markets. The marketing system and farmers' marketing practices have undergone considerable changes during the last 50 years owing to the expansion of the size of the market, increased availability of infrastructure and changes in the pattern of demand and consequently introduction of new methods of processing, packaging, storage and transportation. Farmers' marketing practices and evolution of marketing system are guided by the shelf-life of the commodity. All agricultural products do not have the same shelf-life. Some products are perishable, some are less and some are even durable. Cotton and jute versus fruits, vegetables and milk are contrasting examples of agricultural products having long and short shelf-life. In between these two extremes are other agricultural commodities (Tripathi, A., & Prasad, A. R. 2009). Owing to the increase in marketed surplus and need to make these available in the off-season and at Places other than production points, functions of storage, processing, transportation, packaging and grading are required to be performed either by the farmers or by market functionaries.

Main Characteristics Of Marketing:

Optimization of input use and output produced: Agricultural marketing leads to the optimization of resource use and output

management. An efficient marketing system can contribute to an increase in the marketable surplus by scaling down the losses arising out of the Agricultural Marketing inefficient processing, Storage and transportation. A well-designed system of marketing can effectively distribute the available stock of modern inputs and thereby sustain a faster rate of growth in the agricultural sector.

Increase in farm income: An efficient Marketing system guarantees to the farmers better prices for farm products and induce them to invest their surpluses in the purchase of modern inputs so that productivity may increase. This again results in increase in the marketed surplus and income of the farmers.

Widening of markets: A well known marketing system widens market for products by taking them to remote corners of the country to areas far away from the production point e.g. paddy produced in Punjab and Haryana are sold in remote tribal areas. Another example is potato. The widening of the market helps in increasing the demand on a continuous basis and thereby guarantees a higher income to the producer.

Growth of agro-based industries: The agricultural marketing system helps in the growth of agro-based industries and stimulates the overall development process of the economy. Many industries depend on agriculture for the supply of raw materials e.g. sugar industry, cotton industry, and silk industry.

Price movements: An efficient marketing helps the farmers in planning their production in accordance with the need of the economy. This work is carried out through the price signals.

Adoption and spread of new technology: The marketing system helps the farmers in the adoption of new scientific and technical knowledge.

Employment: The marketing system provides employment to millions of persons engaged in various activities such as packaging, transportation, storage and processing.

Addition to National income: Marketing activities add to the Nation's Gross National Product.

Better living: Any plan of economic development that aims at diminishing the poverty of agricultural population, reducing consumer food prices, earning more foreign exchange or eliminating economic waste has to pay special attention to the development of an efficient marketing for food and agricultural products.

Creation of Utility: Marketing creates the following four types of utilities of the product:

Form Utility: The processing function adds form utility by changing the raw material into finished products e.g. paddy- rice; Wheat-bread, biscuit, cake; Milk ghee, cream, cheese, skimmed milk, butter.

Place Utility: The transportation function adds place utility to products by shifting them to a place of need from the place of plenty e.g. potatoes in plain, milk at urban places.

Time Utility: The storage function adds time utility to the products by making them available at the time when they are needed e.g. tamarind, rice in offseason.

Possession Utility: The marketing functions buying and selling helps in the transfer of ownership of goods from one person to another in the marketing system. The points of view of producer, middlemen, and consumers are different, but each is individualistic and concerned with his profit. From the producer point of view, it is important to know whether the prices prevailing in the market enable him to continue to produce or not, and what he should produce and where and at what time he should sell it. Large-scale production requires skill to sell it at remunerative price. A consumer looks at marketing from the point of view of good and the prices at which they are offered. Middlemen try to increase his profit margin by discharging various marketing functions. Marketing has greater importance and significance for the society as a whole than for any of the individual beneficiaries of the marketing process.

Methodology

The study is primarily based on qualitative systematic review of literature on agricultural marketing developments in India and how

these developments are significant to address the challenges of agriculture marketing systems through adopting proper regulation. Literature has been compiled from various Government reports; scientific journals; online published articles; newspapers and websites of different organizations and institutions working on agricultural marketing. The compiled literature has been sorted out based on status and challenges of efficient marketing in India were the two criteria keeping the objectives in consideration. The literature's were cautiously reviewed further to draw a logical conclusion about the development and reforms in agricultural markets; shortfalls during implementation of reforms in agricultural marketing and the strategies through e-NAM intervention to strengthen the marketing reforms.

Results and Discussion

What is Model Act?

Agriculture marketing is a state subject; hence each state has its own APMC Act. It is creating hindrances in the trace of agricultural commodities. In response to that the Department of Agriculture and Cooperation had formulated and circulated a Model Agricultural Produce Marketing Committee (APMC) Act in 2003, on marketing of agricultural produce for guidance and adoption by the State Governments. The model legislation provides for the establishment of Private Markets/Yards, Direct Purchase Centres, Consumer and Farmers Markets for direct sale and promotion of Public Private Partnership in the management and development of agricultural markets in the country. The Act also provides for the constitution of State Agricultural Produce Marketing Standards Bureau for promotion of Grading, Standardisation and Quality Certification of agricultural produce. This would facilitate pledge financing, direct purchasing, forward and future trading and exports.

Model APMC Act of 2003

The Government of India designed a model Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) Act in 2003 as a first attempt to bring reforms in the agricultural markets. Union Government had prepared a Model APMC Act in 2003. As of 2014 some 16 states have adopted this Model Act. The salient features of this act are as follows:

Provisions under this act were:

1. To establish New market channels other than APMC markets
2. Private wholesale markets
3. Direct purchase
4. A contract for buyers and farmers

The Market Committees under the APMC Act, 2003 was responsible for:

1. Ensuring transparency in transactions, it can lead to better pricing system of the market area
2. To Provide market-led agricultural extension services to farmers
3. Ensuring that farmers to get their payment for their produce sold on the same day.
4. To Promote agricultural processing, it increase the value of the produce in markets
5. Making the availability and dates public on which the agricultural produce is brought to the market
6. Promoting and establishing public-private partnerships (PPP) in these markets.

Execution status of the Act

Midterm Appraisal of the Planning Commission mentioned that twenty five States/ Union Territories have amended their APMC Acts or have made varying provisions for the purpose while other states are in the process of doing so. However the manner of implementation in most states reveals serious weaknesses which discourage the entrance of new players. In many cases the rules have yet to be notified. In some cases permission for direct purchase from farmers is being given for a year at a time which is a clear discouragement to anyone wishing to undertake a sizeable

investment. Several states (about 16) have passed a new Act but only the States of Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Orissa, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh (only for special licence for more than one market), and Haryana (only for contract

farming) have notified the amended rules so far. Tamil Nadu already has provisions for the envisaged reforms and Bihar (act repealed), Kerala, Manipur and the UTs (except Delhi and Puducherry) do not have the APMC Act hence do not require these reforms (table.1).

Table.1. Progress of Reforms in Agricultural Markets (APMC Act) (as on 31 October 2010)

Sl.No	Stage of reforms	Name of State/ Union territory
1	Reforms to the APMC Act have been done for Direct Marketing; Contract Farming and Markets in Private/Coop. Sectors.	Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Mizoram, Nagaland, Orissa, Rajasthan, Sikkim, and Tripura
2	Reforms to APMC Act have been done partially	Direct Marketing: NCT of Delhi Contract Farming: Haryana, Punjab and Chandigarh Private Markets: Punjab and Chandigarh
3	There is no APMC Act and hence not requiring reforms	Bihar*, Kerala, Manipur, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu, and Lakshadweep
4	The APMC Act already provides for reforms	Tamil Nadu
5	Administrative action has been initiated for the reforms	Meghalaya, Haryana, J&K, Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Pondicherry, NCT of Delhi and Uttar Pradesh

Note: * APMC Act has been repealed with effect from September 1, 2006.

Shortcomings in the APMC System

1. The monopoly of APMC – Monopoly of any trade (barring few exceptions) is bad, whether it is by some MNC corporation by government or by any APMC. It deprives farmers of better customers and consumers from original suppliers.

2. Entry Barriers – License fees in these markets are highly prohibitive. In many markets, farmers are not allowed to operate. Further, over and above license fee, rent/value for shops is quite high which keeps away competition. At most places, only a group of the village/urban elite operates in APMC.

3. Cartelization – It is quite often seen that agents in an APMC get together to form a cartel and deliberately restraint from higher bidding. Produce is procured at a manipulatively discovered price and sold at a higher price. Spoils are then shared by participants, leaving farmers in the lurch.

4. High commission due to more number of middle men, taxes, and levies – Farmers have to pay commission, marketing fee, APMC cess which pushes up costs. Apart from this many states impose Value Added Tax.

5. APMC plays the dual role of regulator and Market. Consequently, its role as regulator is undermined by vested interest in the lucrative trade. They despite inefficiency won't let go of any control. Generally, members and chairman are nominated/elected out of the agents operating in that market.

6. Other Manipulations – Agents have a tendency to block a part of the payment for unexplained or fictitious reasons. Farmer is sometimes refused a payment slip (which acknowledges sale and payment) which is essential for him to get a loan.

Opportunities Ahead

First, incentivise the states to ensure that APMC is reformed and notified in all the states for direct buying from farmers; encourage “clustering” of farmers in groups through NGOs, be it in the form of cooperatives, farmers clubs, or contract farming etc. Second, reforming institution improving marketing conditions and encouraging private sector participation, require reforming the Agricultural Produce Marketing Committee (APMC) Act and abolishing the Essential Commodities Act (ECA). (Brithal, P. S., Jha, A. K., & Singh, H. 2007). & (Hota, S. K., Kishor, B., & Sharma, V. 2002). What started as protective regime to prevent the exploitation of farmers in marketing their produce and ensuring fair price, has resulted in excessive government control. Cleaning up these archaic provisions can trigger private sector investments in developing regularised markets, logistics and warehouse receipt systems, futures markets, and in infrastructure (such as cold storage, grades and standards, quality certification, etc) for large domestic markets as well as imports and exports. And this is what is expected by the IMG

on inflation, by entry of the multi brand retail in India (Hoff, K., Braverman, A., & Stiglitz, J. (1993).

In the current situation, the government is compelled to take care of the health of poor and vulnerable sections for which it must undertake procurement and distribution of food and nutritious commodities such as milk, millets, and vegetables on a massive scale. Under the current unprecedented catastrophic situation caused by COVID-19 pandemic, it will be imprudent to dismantle a government-sponsored marketing mechanism for food and agricultural commodities and diluting the very spirit of State intervention that exists strongly behind that institutional arrangement.

Horticulture should be exempted from the APMC Act

With the spectre of high food inflationary haunting the national economy, the confederation of Indian Industry's (CII) National council on agriculture has sought structural changes to augment growth in the horticulture sector. We have been talking about the APMC Act in the 7-8 years. Seventeen states have given a thumbs-up but it is not being implemented in letter and spirit. They have gone about arbitrarily making changes. The pressure of middlemen is also preventing state government from going ahead in full stream. Therefore horticulture has to be exempted from APMC Act.

Farmers should be given the freedom to sell their produce directly to a food processing company, a consolidator or a retailer. Time will be shortened. Opening up of the retail sector is beneficial for the industry as investments in organised retail will scale up the entire supply chain and ensure good prices to farmers as well as consumers (Jha, et al 2015). Fresh produce moves at an ambient temperature, which leads to tremendous wastages. Hence opening up the sector will create infrastructure. When it comes to the implementation of recommendations in the short run, looking at the rising prices of fruits and vegetables, there is a need to lower the existing tariffs and encourage the import of these commodities (Agarwal, 2016). The Government should incentivise private sector- both domestic and foreign, cooperatives and NGOs to come up with business models that directly link the growers with processors and retailers.

The committee of APMC consists of farmers, stakeholders and traders, their responsibility is to managing all buying, selling and proving information. This institutional arrangement comprising of around 50,000 intermediaries with 162 APMCs supposed to protect almost 78 lakh farmers interests with a production of around 170 lakh tonnes of food grains, 68 lakh tonnes of vegetables, and 55 lakh tonnes of fruits annually in Karnataka.

Benefits Of Efficient Marketing

1. **Any increase in the efficiency** of the marketing process, which results in lower costs of distribution and lower prices to consumers, really brings about an increase in the National Income.

2. **A reduction in the cost** of marketing is a direct benefit to the society.

3. **Marketing process brings new varieties**, quality and beneficial goods to consumers. It provides connecting link between production and consumption. Approximately one third of all persons gainfully employed in the country are engaged in the field of marketing and about one fourth of National Income is earned by marketing profession.

4. **Scientific marketing has a stabilizing** effect on the price level. If producers produce what consumers want and consumers have a wide choice of products there are no frequent ups and downs in price.

5. **Marketing is a catalyst** for the transmutation of latent resources in to actual resources, of desires into accomplishments and development of responsible economic leaders and informed economic citizens.

6. **Marketing brings to the farmers useful** implements, tools and fertilizers etc. and the benefits of the use of machines and free after sales service, and make them modern farmers. Scientific marketing also remedies the imbalance in the supply of making available the surpluses to the deficit areas. If the functions of marketing are not performed properly, the economic system may get out of balance resulting in piling up of goods with retailers, wholesalers and manufacturers, which lead to closure of factories and retrenchment of workers. Thus it plays an important role in economic stability of a country.

What is the relation of APMC With eNAM?

The National Agriculture Market (NAM) is a pan-India electronic trading portal, which links the existing Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) mandis across the country to form a unified national market for agricultural commodities (NIAM, 2017 and Nirmal, R. 2017).

In 2018, on March 23rd, regulated agricultural markets has witnessed in 16 States and 2 Union Territories on the electronic platform of e-NAM. Few states such as Karnataka, Sikkim, Assam, Jammu & Kashmir, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Tripura, Mizoram, Manipur, Goa and Kerala didn't join group of e-NAM due to different reasons. However, Karnataka state has adopted its own model named as Rashtriya e Market Services (ReMS).

How APMCs get benefitted from eNAM?

Benefits from eNAM for an APMC are:

1. Free Software for System integration/ Automation of recording transactions
2. Complete information on trade
3. Real-time arrival recording
4. Analyze price trends, arrival and trading activities
5. Automated record of financial information
6. Reduction in manpower requirement

Need For Reforms For Effective Marketing

At present, the farmers produce about 30 to 40% is made available and sold in the APMC yards in regulated markets in the country. However, there is no possibility of guarantee that the market functionaries can deliver the best output in these markets. Hence, the present system has to be upscale and modified according to changing trend such as transparent, competitive and farmer friendly. Hence, there is an immediate need to take the agricultural commodity to near markets as early as possible with a great support by government intervention by creating infrastructure such as village warehouses, roads and processing industries especially at the village level. Apart from these support, legal resource facilitating information for minimum support prices is need for the prevention of purchases and sales of farm produces.

Conclusion

The draft model legislation titled the State Agricultural Produce Marketing (Development and Regulation) Act, 2003, provides for establishment of Private Markets/ yards, Direct Purchase Centres, Consumer/Farmers Markets for direct sale and promotion of Public Private Partnership in the management and development of

agricultural markets in the country. It also provides for separate constitution for Special Markets for commodities like Onions, Fruits, Vegetables, Flowers etc. A separate chapter has been included in the legislation to regulate and promote contract-farming arrangements in the country. It provides for prohibition of commission agency in any transaction of agricultural commodities with the producers. It redefines the role of present Agricultural Produce Market Committee to promote alternative marketing system, contract farming, direct marketing and farmers/consumers markets. It also redefines the role of State Agricultural Marketing Boards to promote standardization, grading, quality certification, market led extension and training of farmers and market functionaries in marketing related areas. Provision has also been made in the Act for constitution of State Agricultural Produce Marketing Standards Bureau for promotion of Grading, Standardization and Quality Certification of Agricultural Produce. This would facilitate pledge financing, E-trading, direct purchasing, export, forward/future trading and introduction of negotiable warehousing receipt system in respect of agricultural commodities. It is hoped that the model legislation will enable nationwide integration of agricultural markets, facilitate emergence of competitive agricultural markets in private and cooperative sectors, create environment conducive to massive investments in marketing related infrastructure and lead to modernization and strengthening of existing markets. An efficient agricultural marketing is essential for the development of the agriculture sector as it provides outlets and incentives for increased production, the marketing system contribute greatly to the commercialization of subsistence farmers. There is a necessity to integrate farm production with national and international markets to enable farmers to undertake market driven production plan and adoption of modern marketing practices.

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